

WORKSHOP 1: SYSTEMS MAPPING

Date: 24.02.2024

Duration: 4 hours

Number of participants: 8 people

Profile of participants: Young people 22-27 years old, residing in Germany (Thuringia or Saxony-Anhalt) coming from EU and non-EU countries, and one representative of an NGO, working on sustainable agriculture with young people

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Workshop Report

The first workshop started with the welcome word from the facilitator. The Learning Community participants already knew each other from the previous project activities, so the warm-up round was short.

Photo of the Learning Community meeting on 24.02.24 taken by Zafar Saydaliev.

In order to update everyone on the current progress of the PLANET4B project, the facilitator showed a few slides, bringing into the focus the research questions of the Urban Youth Case.

Looking at the two questions on the slide, the facilitator asked to discuss them in pairs and write down the key findings of each dyad. This helped to kick-start the thinking about the case and made the smooth transition to the next task.

The participants raised the following points:

1. **Real-life priorities vs. biodiversity:** Participants noted the challenge of prioritising biodiversity and sustainable practices in daily life, especially when dealing with immediate concerns like job

security and economic stability. The conversation highlighted a general agreement that “personal survival” often takes precedence over environmental concerns.

2. **Experiential learning creates emotional bonds:** The importance of engaging activities, such as outdoor interventions, games, and workshops, was emphasised. Such experiences were seen as crucial for creating emotional bonds to the topic of biodiversity, making learning more impactful and memorable.
3. **Empowerment and privilege:** There was a significant discussion on the difficulty of feeling empowered to make a change, especially for less privileged individuals. The dialogue included concerns about the disproportionate impact of affluent individuals compared to those with fewer resources and how systemic inequality affects people's capacity to act on environmental issues.
4. **The impact of economic and survival concerns:** The group discussed how “survival mode”, a state where individuals are focused on immediate needs, limits the capacity for broader environmental concerns. The conversation touched on scientific findings that suggest survival mode alters brain function, reducing the ability to engage with long-term issues like biodiversity.
5. **Volunteering as a way of engaging with nature:** Volunteering was proposed as a potential way to get involved with nature conservation. However, the need for institutional support to make such volunteering viable without sacrificing living standards was highlighted. There were discussions about existing programs for youth in some countries (in Germany – FÖJ or BFD), but the need for broader and more accessible initiatives was emphasised.
6. **The role of social and economic systems:** The group also talked about the need for a shift in how society values agricultural work and community involvement in food production. The conversation touched on the potential for urban agriculture and community gardens to address multiple social issues, including community cohesion and mental health.
7. **Systemic changes and political action:** There was a call for more systemic changes and political action to prioritise environmental programs and support for volunteering. The participants discussed the challenge of influencing government priorities and the importance of advocacy and lobbying for environmental causes.
8. **Simplification of environmental actions:** A key suggestion was to simplify environmental actions into manageable steps to make it easier for individuals to incorporate sustainable practices into their lives, combating the feeling of being overwhelmed by the scale of environmental problems.

Photos of the Learning Community meeting on 24.02.24 taken by Maryna Bykova.

After each pair presented the results of their discussion, the facilitator proceeded with the task from the "Methodology Guide for Task 3.2". The emphasis was made on identifying two types of factors, direct and distal ones. Afterwards, the facilitator gave the group 30 minutes to draw the onion diagram and discuss the factors.

The following ideas were mentioned during the discussion:

1. **Health concerns:** The discussion opened with an acknowledgment of health concerns among young people, including mental and physical health issues, highlighting how these concerns could influence their engagement with environmental and biodiversity topics.
2. **Economic factors and security:** Participants discussed the importance of economic factors, such as financial investments and economic security, emphasising that primary needs like food and shelter take precedence over environmental concerns. The notion that economic instability or insecurity can hinder engagement with biodiversity was highlighted.
3. **Education:** Education was discussed as a direct influencer, not limited to formal schooling but also encompassing general awareness and understanding of environmental issues.
4. **Global influences:** Global markets and political climates were identified as indirect influencers, shaping day-to-day decisions and long-term perspectives on environmental engagement.
5. **Social and political structures:** The conversation ventured into the role of social and political structures in shaping environmental engagement. The discussion pointed out that certain social and political conditions, historically and currently, have fostered or hindered societies' ability to engage with environmental sustainability.
6. **Colonisation and power dynamics:** A critical view on Europe's rise as a global powerhouse was expressed, attributing it significantly to colonisation and exploitation rather than just geographical or climatic advantages. The conversation briefly touched on the technological advancements that enabled colonisation and the societal pressures that drove European nations to expand and exploit other regions.
7. **Intersectionality and environmental engagement:** The concept of intersectionality was indirectly touched upon, with discussions on how various identities and social positions, such as being a migrant or belonging to a disadvantaged group, affect individuals' capacity and willingness to engage in environmental activism.
8. **The role of citizenship:** Citizenship was discussed as a factor that influences an individual's ability to engage in political and environmental activism. The discussion acknowledged the limitations and opportunities provided by one's citizenship status in participating in democracy and environmental movements.
9. **Social media and personal relationships:** The influence of social media and personal relationships on shaping young people's views and engagement with biodiversity was noted. These factors were recognized for their potential to both inspire and deter young individuals from environmental activism.

Photo of the Learning Community meeting on 24.02.24 taken by Fatima Azadli.

Each of the participants then took a sticky-note and wrote down the discussed factors. Next, all the notes were placed on the diagram and the group had a moment to look at the whole system. The facilitator asked a round of follow-up questions in order to see if some notes could be clustered or if new ideas appear.

Photos of the Learning Community meeting on 24.02.24 taken by Fatima Azadli.

When there were no more changes wished from the participants' side, the facilitator asked two volunteers to present the developed system. A video was recorded for this purpose. After the break, the participants came back to the session, and had a go with the optional tasks.

The members of the Learning Community were asked the following questions:

- *Where in the system are the flows of knowledge, information, influence, money, people?*
- *Which components are related to which other components in the system?*
- *How are the components interrelated? Do they influence each other either positively (+) or negatively (-)?*

The discussion started with acknowledging the complexity of interconnections between various factors influencing young people's engagement with biodiversity and environmental issues.

The following points were made:

1. **Influence of digitalisation:** The participants discussed the dual impact of digitalisation on environmental engagement. On one hand, digitalisation can facilitate awareness and education about environmental issues; on the other hand, it can lead to decreased direct engagement with nature.
2. **Impact of urban settings:** Urban infrastructures were identified as both a barrier and a facilitator to engagement with biodiversity. Poor urban planning can lead to a lack of green spaces, negatively affecting mental health and limiting opportunities for interaction with nature.
3. **Economic security:** Economic security, or rather the lack thereof, was recognised as a significant factor influencing young people's capacity to prioritise environmental concerns. Financial instability can overshadow the perceived importance of biodiversity.
4. **Citizenship and empowerment:** Citizenship status was discussed as a factor affecting one's ability to engage in environmental activism. Participants noted that lack of citizenship can make

individuals feel less empowered to participate in political and environmental decision-making processes.

5. **Role of education:** Education was highlighted as a critical entry point for engaging young people with biodiversity. The participants noted, however, that the current education system might not sufficiently emphasise the importance of biodiversity and could benefit from more hands-on, outdoor learning experiences.
6. **Global climate change:** The global climate crisis was acknowledged as both an indirect and direct influencer of young people's engagement with biodiversity. It was mentioned that climate change could lead to eco-anxiety, affecting mental health and potentially motivating or deterring action.
7. **Migration and conflict:** The participants touched on the role of migration and conflict external factors of influence. Forced migration due to conflict or climate change can bring about new challenges and opportunities for environmental activism.
8. **Technological revolution:** The technological revolution was discussed as a factor with both positive and negative impacts on biodiversity. While it can facilitate monitoring and education, it can also lead to new forms of waste and pollution.

The arrows were drawn to point out different flows, the money sign was added when it was referred as monetary influence. Red line referred to positive influence, and blue for negative.

Photo of the Learning Community meeting on 24.02.24 taken by Fatima Azdli.

The extra task brought new ideas to the system map, which appeared as new (different colour) sticky-notes on the onion diagram.

Photos of the Learning Community meeting on 24.02.24 taken by Fatima Azadli.

The final onion diagram looked as following:

The voice-recording about the flow compilation is also available for the analysis.

Overall, the workshop helped the Learning Community to understand the scale of the case better and prepared for the next steps with introducing the leverage points and interventions methods.